

Research Article

Public Health Effects of Effluent Discharge of Kaduna Refinery into River Romi

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ABSTRACT

The study examines public health effects of effluent discharge of Kaduna refinery on River Romi. The study carried out in two years (2010 to 2011) had water samples collected in two seasons (rainy and dry seasons) and a range of physico-chemical and microbial parameters were measured. The results reveal that all the parameters measured were far and above the World Health Organization (WHO) maximum permissible limits, the study identified potential health effects of the presence of these parameters in the water of River Romi. The significance of water to the health and well-being of human populations is increasingly apparent. Water pollution particularly from industrial effluents is a worldwide problem and its potential to influence the health of human populations is great.

There is no doubt that excessive levels of pollution are causing a lot of damage to human and animal health.

Keywords: Water pollution, Public health, Effluent Discharge, River Romi, Parameters

INTRODUCTION

All peoples, whatever their stage of development and social and economic condition, have the right to have access to drinking-water in quantities and of a quality equal to their basic needs. (WHO, 2004)

Over the last three decades there has been increasing global concern over the public health impacts attributed to water pollution, in particular, the global burden of disease. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that about a quarter of the diseases facing mankind today occur due to prolonged exposure to water pollution. Most of these water pollution-related diseases are however not easily detected and may be acquired during childhood and manifested later in adulthood.

The discharge of industrial effluent into water bodies is one of the main causes of environmental pollution and degradation in many cities, especially in developing countries. Many of these industries lack liquid and solid waste regulations and proper disposal facilities, including for harmful waste. Such waste may be infectious, toxic or radioactive. (World Health Organization [WHO], 2004).

In most countries the principal risks to human health associated with the consumption of polluted water are microbiological in nature as well as chemical contamination. As indicated in Chapter 18 of "Agenda 21" of UNCED, "An estimated 80% of all diseases and over one-third of deaths in developing countries are caused by the consumption of contaminated water and on average as much as one-tenth of each person's productive time is sacrificed to water-related diseases."

The risk of acquiring a waterborne infection increases with the level of contamination by chemicals and pathogenic microorganisms. However, the relationship is not necessarily a simple one and depends very much on factors such as infectious dose and host susceptibility. Pollution reaches its most serious proportions in the densely settled urban-industrial centers of the more developed countries. In poor countries of the world more than 80% polluted water have been used for irrigation with only seventy to eighty percent food and living security in industrial urban and semi urban areas. Industry, clustered in urban and semi-urban areas surrounded by densely populated, low-income localities, continues to pollute the environment with impunity. (European Public Health Alliance, 2009)

The water we drink are essential ingredients for our wellbeing and a healthy life.

Unfortunately polluted water and air are common throughout the world (European Public Health Alliance, 2009). The WHO states that one sixth of the world's population, approximately 1.1 billion people do not have access

to safe water and 2.4 billion lack basic sanitation . Polluted water consists of Industrial discharged effluents, sewage water, rain water pollution and polluted by industries, agriculture or households cause damage to human health or the environment.. This water pollution affects the health and quality of soils and vegetation. Some water pollution effects are recognized immediately, whereas others don't show up for months or years (Ashraf et al, 2010). Estimation indicates that more than fifty countries of the world with an area of twenty million hectares area are treated with polluted or partially treated polluted water including parts of all continents and this poor quality water causes health hazard and death of human being, aquatic life and also disturbs the production of different crops. In fact, the effects of water pollution are said to be the leading cause of death for humans across the globe, moreover, water pollution affects our oceans, lakes, rivers, and drinking water, making it a widespread and global concern (Gauderman et al, 2005). A drinking water contained a fluoride content ranging from 5.26 to 26.32 milligrams per liter and this is too high as compared to the World Health Organization's standard of 0.6 to 1.7 milligram per liter (Gauderman et al, 2005).

In present scenario due to industrialization and increased population, the drains of Nigeria carry the industrial and municipal effluents that are ultimately carried that polluted water to the canals and rivers. The untreated industrial and municipal wastes have created multiple environmental hazards for mankind, irrigation, drinking and sustenance of aquatic life. The drainage water contains heavy metals in addition to biological contaminations. This water pollution infected our food in addition to groundwater contamination when used to irrigate crops and poses great risks to public health.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The study aims at analyzing the public health effects of effluent discharged from Kaduna refinery into the water of river Romi.

OBJECTIVES:

- i. To evaluate the physico-chemical and microbial quality of water in River Romi.
- ii. To assess the level at which oil related effluents discharged from the refinery affect the quality of water of River Romi
- iii. To compare the quantity of pollutants in the water with the acceptable limits of National Standard and WHO
- iv. To establish the potential public health threat the water could have

Study Area

River Romi is one of the tributary of River Kaduna; it is located in the southern part of Kaduna metropolis between latitude 10° to 11° North and longitude 7° to 8° East, River Romi follow a course of about 16.4 km.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study adopted the work of Vivan, Adamu and Ndahi (2012) who carried out a study on the effects of effluent discharged by Kaduna refinery on the water quality of River Romi. Though the authors took same water samples to the laboratory for microbial analysis.

Water sampling

Collection of water samples was done in the morning between 8am and 9am. Theses samples were collected using Grab method which according to World Bank (1988); Samples were collected into clean 1 litre plastic bottles and were stored in an ice box of 4°C and were taken to the laboratory within twenty-four hours for analysis. Water samples were collected by lowering pre-cleaned plastic bottles into the bottom of the water body, 30 cm deep, and allowed to over flow before withdrawing. Six sampling points were used and the sampling points are approximately 2kms away from each other. A total of 24 samples were analyzed. Four samples were collected from each of the six sampling points. The first location was 2km up stream, the second location was at the refinery waste water discharge point. The third to the sixth locations were at the 2kms, 4kms, 6kms and 8kms down stream. The study was carried out through two (2) years 2010 and 2011. Thus, six samples were collected during the rainy season (July 2010), six during the dry season (March 2010), another six during the rainy season (August 2011) and the last six during the

dry season (February 2011). Parameters investigated are those indicating effects of oil related effluents on water quality.

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL ANALYSES

The physico-chemical parameters were determined according to procedures outlined in the Standard Method for the Examination of Water and Waste water (APHA, 1998). As indicated in the sampling, the parameters analyzed are those believed to have effects on water quality and referred to by WHO (2004). These parameters are Electrical conductivity, Suspended Solids, Dissolved Solids, Total Solids, pH, Dissolved Oxygen, Biochemical Oxygen Demand, (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), and Oil and Grease. Two basic techniques were used: Gravimetric, Volumetric techniques. The gravimetric technique was used to analyze Total Solids, Dissolved Solids and Suspended Solids, while the volumetric technique was used to determine the concentration of BOD, COD and Oil and Grease.

Table 1: Mean Values of physico-chemical parameters for two years (2010 – 2011)

Parameter	Points of collecting water sample						Maximum Permissible Limits	
	Up stream 2km	Point of entry 0km	2km	4km	6km	8km	National Standard (NIGERIA)*	WHO*
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/l)	9.8	2	6	7	8	9	10	10
Biochemical Oxygen Demand (mg/l)	15	260	210	160	110	100	10	10
Chemical Oxygen Demand (mg/l)	42	80	70	65	50	50	40	40
Dissolved Solids (mg/l)	300	400	600	400	200	250	200	250
Suspended Solids (mg/l)	40	100	120	80	60	70	30	30
Total Solids (mg/l)	150	195	180	173	160	150	150	NA
Oil & Grease (mg/l)	3.5	20.5	10.2	9.6	6.2	4.0	10.6	NA
Conductivity ($\mu\text{m/cm}$)	250	300	260	240	255	350	240	250
Ph	6.9	3.5	5.0	5.4	6.0	6.5	6.5-8	6.5-8
Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	36	38	36	35	34	33	30	30
Turbidity (NTU^1)	3	6	5	5	5	5	5	5
Benzene (mg/l)	0.00	2.5	2.1	1.8	1.2	0.8	NA	0.001
Cyanide (mg/l)	0.02	0.5	0.62	0.21	0.10	0.08	NA	0.07
Mercury (mg/l)	0.001	0.5	0.20	0.15	0.09	0.05	NA	0.001
Cadmium (mg/l)	0.003	0.024	0.013	0.009	0.006	0.004	NA	0.003

Source: Adopted from Vivan, Adamu and Ndahi (2012)

* National Standard (NIGERIA) and World Health Organization maximum acceptable limits

NA= Not Available

Table 2: Toxic heavy metals present in River Romi and established health effects.

Physico-chemical	Average Quantity in water sample	Maximum Permissible Limits		Potential Health Effects
		National Standard (NIGERIA)*	WHO*	
Benzene (mg/l)	1.4	NA	0.001	Women and children are most vulnerable Have carcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogenic effects. In humans, these metal can produce kidney and liver disorders, damage the central nervous system Cause blindness.
Cyanide (mg/l)	0.255	NA	0.07	Exposure lead to pneumonitis, branchitis muscle tumor, irritability, gingivitis Nerve damage Enter to the food chain and concentrated In humans, these metal can produce kidney and liver disorders, weaken the bone structure, damage the central nervous system Cause blindness, and lead to death
Mercury (mg/l)	0.17	NA	0.001	Gastro-intestinal disorders, respiratory tract irritation, renal failure and neurotoxicity
Lead (mg/l)	0.11	NA	0.01	Impairment of neurological development, suppression of the haematological system and kidney failure
Nitrate (mg/l)	62	NA	50	Harmful to health
Phosphate (mg/l)	45	NA	NA	Harmful to health
Ammonium (mg/l)	0.8	NA	0.1	Harmful to health
Sulphate (mg/l)	275	NA	250	Acute effects such as eye and respiratory irritation

Source: laboratory analysis 2011

* National Standard (NIGERIA) and World Health Organization (WHO) maximum acceptable limits

NA = Not Available

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The table 1 reveals that the Dissolved oxygen (D.O) content of the water samples indicated that while it is almost normal in the up stream sample (9.8 mg/l), at the point of entry of effluent the DO decreased drastically to 2.0 mg/l and was increasing as it moves further down stream.

The concentration of Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) do not conform with the maximum acceptable limit for inland waters as earmarked by WHO (2004), as 10 mg/l and 40 mg/l are the respective acceptable limits, even the upstream values shows 15 mg/l and 42 mg/l respectively for BOD and COD, it also shows that the BOD value are very high even at the 8km point down stream where the value is suppose to be lower but the results indicates 100 mg/l which is ten times higher than the National Standard acceptable limit, the highest BOD value was obtained at the point of entry.

From table 1, it shows that it is only at the up stream that the values conform to National Standard acceptable limits as the up stream value is 150 mg/l, there was an increase in value at the point of entry and then gradual decrease in value as go further down stream. In the same vein, the values of Dissolved Solids obtained are quite high in all the sample collection points up stream and down stream along the river.

The suspended solids also remained at high at all sample collections points throughout the entire periods of study as against the National Standard acceptable limit of 30 mg/l, upstream, the value recorded was 40 mg/l.

Oil and grease fall within the acceptable limit of 10.6 mg/l, the results shows that up stream the value is 3.5 mg/l and at 8 km down stream the value is 4.0mg/l, there is a serious raise in the content of oil and grease at the point of entry which has a value of 20.1 mg/l as compared to values at other points of collecting samples.

For electrical conductivity the results indicated that only the 4 km down stream sample point was anything close to National Standard acceptable limits at the other points the values were high and well above National Standard acceptable limit.

Refinery waste-water, has a BOD of 2500 – 3000 mg/l which is 10 times the strength of domestic waste-water. This means that 1m³ of refinery effluent pollutes a river to the same degree as 10m³ of raw domestic effluent;

From table 1 the pH values of four sampling points deviates from the National Standard acceptable limit of 6.5, apart from the values of 6 km and 8 km down stream sampling point, the rest show high acidity with the point of entry being the highest with a value of 3.5.

The table shows that the temperature of water samples at all collection points is said to be tolerable when compared to National Standard acceptable limits.

MACROBIAL WATER QUALITY

The results obtained for the microbial analysis reveals that the microbial water quality of River Romi is poor, total and faecal coliforms pollution are wide spread and the entire course of the river as sampled is not suitable for domestic consumption without treatment. For agricultural uses there is a possibility of contamination from vegetables and other crops eaten in their raw state. The mean total coliforms and the faecal coliforms is quite high, this is unacceptable when compared to the World Health Organization (WHO) permissible limits. The results have revealed faecal pollution of the water in river Romi and this implies that the water pose a serious health risk to man, animals and plants. The poor microbiological quality of the water in river Romi might be due to the effluents discharged from kaduna refinery into the river.

Similarly table 2 reveals the potential health threat the presence of these heavy metals found in the water pose to man and animals, as their mean values are far and above the World Health Organization maximum permissible limits.

CONCLUSION

This study has linked water pollution to public health. Water samples analyzed from all the sample collection points along the river course apart from the 2km collection point up stream show high levels of heavy metals emanating from the effluents discharged by the refinery in particular lead, mercury, cadmium, copper and chromium. Though, a medical evaluation of the children and adults living and schooling near the river is yet to be conducted to associate prevalent diseases in the area with high exposure levels to these metal pollutants and microbial.

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